

LONG TERM RELIABILITY OF CFRPs IN BRIDGE ENGINEERING

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Keywords: CFRP cables, rehabilitation, structural health monitoring

ABSTRACT

Corrosion and in certain cases also fatigue in steel is seriously bothering bridge owners since more than a century. Therefore institutions in Europe, USA, Canada and Japan proposed in the 1980ties the use of non-metallic structural elements.

Starting from 1991 pilot projects with CFRP applications have been initiated in bridge construction. Most noticeable is the Verdasio Bridge with its very high sustained stress of 1610 MPa in the CFRP post-tensioning tendons.

The application of carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) in construction, especially in post-strengthening and rehabilitation is today well known and highly appreciated in most parts of the world due to its long-term reliability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Corrosion on suspender-, main- and stay-cables made of steel is seriously bothering bridge owners at least since the 1980ties [1, 2]. Additionally fatigue and especially fretting fatigue are severe problems in the cases of steel suspender- and stay-cables [3, 4]. In many cases also post- and pre-tensioning elements, as well as classical steel reinforcing bars are concerned [5]. Therefore researchers in Europe, USA, Canada and Japan proposed in the 1980ties and early 90ties the use of non-metallic tendons and reinforcing bars including CFRPs [6-14]. At the beginning it sounded totally irrational to use such expensive materials like CFRPs in civil construction. Only few bridge owners and responsible authorities have been willing since 1991 [15] to support the application of CFRPs under the condition that the long term behaviour of concerned structures was going to be conscientiously monitored by means of structural health monitoring (SHM) [16].

Almost a quarter century passed now since world's first application of CFRPs in construction on Ibach Bridge near Lucerne in Switzerland. Based on the excellent experience in practice CFRPs have meanwhile been fully established as state-of-the-art within the domain of rehabilitation of structures in construction industry. However it was a long way to go. On the other hand the first ideas for CFRP applications were not thought for tasks in rehabilitation; it was much more new construction [17]. Like in rehabilitation of civil structures also the relatively few existing new constructions with CFRPs proved to be very reliable. However up to now there has been due to the high initial cost no commercial break-through in the domain of new construction.

2 CFRPS SUPPORT REHABILITATION OF CIVIL STRUCTURES

2.1 Case Ibach Bridge

The Ibach Bridge was world's first civil structure being post-strengthened with carbon fibre reinforced polymer strips. It is located near Lucerne/Switzerland. It crosses over the National Highway A2 (connecting Germany with Italy) and the rivers Emme and Reuss. The bridge was designed as a continuous beam structure with 7 spans and a total length of 228 m. In the span that crosses the six

lanes of the National Highway A2 a large post-tensioning cable in a web was accidentally cut. The repair work was undertaken in the summer of 1991. Three CFRP strips with a total mass of 6.5 kg were bonded to the soffit of the bridge girder replacing the cut steel cable. In order to have obtained the same results with steel plates, 175 kg would have been necessary. Results of loading tests show that experimentally measured strains agree with the calculated values. For the loading test and the long term strain monitoring program 32 as called “demec points” (pre-drilled stainless steel discs) have been attached to the soffit of the bridge girder with adhesive. Eight gauge lengths were on concrete and the other eight pair wise in parallel on one of the three CFRP strips.

The “demec gauge” system (Figures 1-4) is a mechanical strain gauge system. It was developed as a reliable and accurate way of taking strain measurements at different points on a structure using a single instrument. Empa scientists are using this kind of devices in the laboratories and on construction sites since about one hundred years. The system consists of an invar main beam with two conical locating points, one fixed and the other pivoting on a special knife edge. The points locate in pre-drilled stainless steel discs that are attached to the structure with adhesive. The movement of the pivoting point is to day measured by a photoelectric incremental length measuring device [18] which is attached to a base plate on the invar beam. Design is such that thermal movement within the instrument is negligible. It has a digital readout of 0.001 mm resolution and can be connected wireless to a lap top computer. The mechanical strain gauge system is ideal for use on many types of structures for strain measurement and crack monitoring. The gauge length in all cases discussed in the following sections is 200 mm. The principle of interpretation of the results of the long term strain measurement is explained in the following section.

Since twenty-four years the CFRP post-strengthening technique performed perfectly well at busy Ibach Bridge under high traffic loads. Opponents of this method predicted in 1991 early failure as a result of weakening of the bond due to water take up of the adhesive, because of temperature cycling, as a consequence of fatigue cycling, because of vandalism and so on. Nothing like that happened.

2.2 Case Oberriet Bridge

The two-lane Oberriet Bridge, build in 1963, crossing the border between Switzerland and Austria, links Oberriet to Meiningen. It crosses the river Rhine in 3 spans, 35-45-35 m as continuous steel/concrete composite girder (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: View from underneath the Oberriet Bridge with the laterally post-strengthened concrete deck with CFRP strips (black). Long term strain measurement with “demec gauges” (Figures 2-4).

Thorough investigations had shown that beside regular maintenance the concrete bridge deck was in need of transversal strengthening. This was obviously due to the fact that in 1963 the deck was designed for the standard 140 kN truck load.

In 1996 this standard truck load was 280 kN for this type of bridge. A total of 160 CFRP strips, each 80 mm wide, 1.2 mm thick and 4.2 m long were applied to the soffit of the deck with a spacing of 75 cm. The project is described in more detail in [19]. A typical arrangement of “demec points” is shown in Fig. 2. Figures 3 and 4 show the demec device and a demec point.

Figure 2: With caps protected demec measuring points for long term strain measurement on and beside the CFRP strips. Gauge length (arrow): 200 mm.

Figure 3: Wi-Fi demec measuring device for long term strain measurements on and beside the CFRP strips. Gauge length: 200 mm.

Figure 4: “demec point” glued to a CFRP strip, ready for measurements with the device in Fig. 3.

The change in strain as shown in Fig. 5 is due to change in temperature from summer to winter. As long as the strain lines proceed parallel there is perfect composite action between the concrete soffit and the CFRP strips. In general there is a good correspondence of the strain with the temperature as can be expected. These results are fully satisfactory. No long term drift is observable.

2.3 Case Historic Covered Wooden Bridge in Sins

The historic covered wooden bridge in Sins (Figures 6, 7 and 8), constructed in 1807, crosses the River Reuss and consists of two spans, each of 30.8 m length. Problems arose with the crossbeams (Fig. 7). Under the permissible load of 200 kN per vehicle the oak crossbeams exhibited excessive deflections. To limit these deflections the beams subjected to the highest loads were successfully stiffened in 1992 with CFRP strips.

The deflection of the cross beams reinforced with CFRP strips (T700S fibres) with an modulus of elasticity of 165 GPa was reduced by approximately 20%, while the deflection of the beams reinforced with the CFRP strips (M 46J fibres) with an modulus of elasticity of 300 GPa was reduced by 50%. The fact that the strengthened cross beams of the Sins Bridge have been subjected to high fatigue loading delivered real-life experience and generated confidence in the CFRP strip method for the preservation of historic wooden structures.

Similar to Ibach and Oberriet Bridge demec points have been installed on the CFRP strips and on the wooden crossbeams. In contrast to the reinforced concrete Oberriet Bridge where the temperature fluctuation has a strong influence on the strains, the temperature has almost no influence on the strains in this wooden bridge. The results show that the strong influence factor is humidity. A good correspondence between the strains and humidity cycle can be observed (for details see [20]). The results reveal a perfect composite action between the oak wood and the CFRP strips at all times. Also these results are highly satisfactory.

Figure 5: Typical results of strain measurement over a period of 10 years. The dashed line corresponds to the temperature. The solid lines connecting circles, triangles and squares correspond to strains. Note: MD = micro strains; 1000 MD = 1 0/00.

Figure 6: Elevation of the Historic Covered Wooden Bridge in Sins.

Figure 7: Cross section of Sins Bridge with post-strengthened crossbeams.

Figure 8: Inside of Sins Bridge.

2.4 Pre-stressed CFRP strips

In most civil engineering applications the CFRP strips are going to be applied in a loose manner. However, also the technique of pre-tensioned CFRP strips, developed at Empa, is applied these days [21-26]. The fatigue life of steel reinforced girders can significantly be improved with the application of pre-stressed CFRP strips due to very effective unloading of the internal steel reinforcing bars. Today there are about one dozen, more or less accepted, of such systems available. However, the high technical advantages of pre-stressed CFRP strips followed up to now no real commercial breakthrough. One reason might be that highly qualified staff is needed to provide this service.

2.5 Reasons for the great success of the CFRP post-strengthening method

Since 1991 the post-strengthening of civil structures with CFRP strips is gaining increasingly in importance. Externally bonded steel plates have in most cases been replaced by CFRP strips. Even when the price for CFRPs by volume is about ten times that of steel, rehabilitation with CFRPs is in most cases less expensive than rehabilitation with steel plates. The reason is the savings in labour hours due the very easy going application. Post-strengthening with CFRP strips is nowadays a state-of-the-art technique in most countries of the world. If the strength is decisive, 1kg of CFRP strips replaces 30 kg of steel plates. The sentence “Never before has a post-strengthening method done so much with so little“, coined in 1997, symbolizes the situation [27].

3 TENDONS MADE OF CFRPs

3.1 Anchorage problems

Tendons made of CFRPs are in general build-up as bundles of pultruded wires or layups of tapes. In most cases the fiber alignment is unidirectional. Tendons are one of the most effective applications of CFRPs; however there is the very difficult task to anchor them successfully. In the following sections the “gradient anchorage” and the “pin-loaded non-laminated strap elements” are going to be presented.

3.2 Gradient anchorage for CFRP parallel wire bundles

Empa researchers have been developing CFRP cables using a conical resin-cast termination. The evaluation of the casting material to fill the space between the cone of the termination and the CFRP wires was the key to the problem. This casting material, also called load transfer media (LTM) has to satisfy multiple requirements: (i) the load should be transferred without reduction of the high long time static and fatigue strength of the CFRP wires due to the connection. (ii) galvanic corrosion between the

CFRP wires and the steel cone of the termination must be avoided. It would harm the steel cone. Therefore the LTM must be an electrical insulator.

Figures 9a and b: Stress build-up in LTM.

The conical shape inside the socket provides the necessary radial pressure to increase the interlaminar shear strength of the CFRP wires. The concept is demonstrated in the Figures 9a and 9b using for this example a one-wire-system. If the LTM over the whole length of the sockets is a highly filled epoxy resin there will be a high shear stress concentration at the beginning of the termination on the surface of the CFRP wire (Fig. 9a). This shear peak causes pull-out or tensile failure far below the strength of the CFRP wire. One could avoid this shear peak by the use of an unfilled soft resin. However this would cause creep and an early stress-rupture.

The best design is shown in Fig. 9b. The LTM is a gradient material. At the load side of the termination the modulus of elasticity is low and continuously increases until reaching a maximum. The LTM is composed of aluminium oxide ceramic (Al_2O_3) granules with a typical diameter of 2 millimetres. All granules have the same size. To get a low modulus of the LTM the granules are coated with a thick layer of epoxy resin and cured before application (Fig. 10, left, top). Hence shrinkage can be avoided later in the socket. To obtain a medium modulus the granules are coated with a thin layer. To reach a high modulus the granules are filled into the socket without any coating (Fig. 10 left, bottom). With this method the modulus of the LTM can be designed tailor-made. The holes between the granules are after all filled by vacuum-assisted resin transfer moulding with epoxy resin [28].

Figure 10: Gradient anchorage system for CFRP wires.

3.3 CFRP tendons as pin-loaded non-laminated strap elements

A carbon fibre reinforced laminated pin-loaded strap, as shown in Figure 11(a), provides a practical tendon for many applications in civil engineering. Such an element can consist of unidirectional CFRPs, having a fibre volume fraction of about 60%, wound around two cylindrical steel pins in a racetrack shape. The maximum number of layers is limited by technical considerations in the manufacturing process [29]. No machining of holes is required to make a strap. The two pins transfer tensile load between the structure, and the fully consolidated strap.

Figure: 11 Conceptual designs of pin-loaded strap elements.

Laboratory experiments and analytical modelling [29] have shown that there are severe stress concentrations in the region where the strap and the pin meet. The tensile resistance of the strap is therefore limited to about 50 % of the material's expected unidirectional strength. This is attributed to stress concentrations, which lead to premature failure. Furthermore, the production process for multi-layered laminated straps is not straightforward, if fibre misalignment is to be eliminated where the stress concentrations occur.

An alternative option to reduce the undesirable stress concentrations, overcome the manufacturing difficulties and to reduce cost is the use of a non-laminated strap. The concept that has been patented [30] is shown in Figure 11(b).

The CFRP strap now comprises a number of unidirectional reinforced layers, formed from a single, continuous, thermoplastic tape of about 0.13 mm thickness. The tape is wound around the two pins and only the end of the outermost layer is fusion bonded to the next outermost layer to form a closed loop.

The non-laminated strap element enables the individual layers to move relative to each other that allows an equalization of forces in the layers as the strap is tensioned [29]. The stress concentrations are reduced since the new structural form is more compliant than the laminated equivalent. Control of the initial tensioning process reduces interlaminar shear stresses so that a more uniform strain distribution in all layers can be achieved. The approach allows greater flexibility in terms of the geometry of the tendon, and it can be manufactured on site. Moreover, the concept is going to be less expensive because there is no consolidation process required.

3.4 Case Verdasio Bridge

The Verdasio Bridge (Figures 12 and 13) in the south of Switzerland is a two-lane highway bridge and was built in the seventies. The length of the continuous two-span girder is 69 m. A large internal post-tensioning steel cable positioned in a concrete web was fully corroded as a result of the use of salt for deicing. It had to be replaced in December 1998.

The refurbishment of the Verdasio Bridge represented the first attempt to make practical use of the results of extensive experiments performed in the 1990's on continuous two-span beams post-tensioned with CFRP cables. Smooth wires were, however, used in place of the CFRP strands described in [31], with the same anchorage system as in [28]. Four external CFRP cables arranged in a polygonal layout at the inner face of the affected web inside (Figures 12b and 13) of the box replaced the corroded steel cross section. Each cable was made up of 19 pultruded CFRP wires with a diameter of 5 mm. The cables are equipped with load cells to measure the post-tensioning force in function of time.

Figure 12a: View of Verdasio Bridge.

Figure 12b: Longitudinal section with polygonal layout of the CFRP cables, all measurements are in [m].

Figure 13: Cross sections of Verdasio Bridge.

The main problem in this application was to tension the cable around relatively tight bending radii of 4.5 m, as CFRP wires are sensitive to transverse pressure due to their composition. However, a series of Empa experiments with 3.0 m radii suggest that a satisfactory solution was found to this problem in Verdasio.

The cable load (Figure 14) and the relative displacement within the anchorages (Figure 15) in function of the time were measured. This project was as far most interesting as in this case the nominal post-tensioning stress in the cable cross sections is as high as 1610 MPa. More similar pilote projets have been presented in [32].

Parallel with the seasonal temperature fluctuation there is a fluctuation of the cable force (Figure 14). The coefficient of thermal expansion for the CFRP tendons is about zero. In summertime, when the temperature is high, the concrete of the bridge girder expands. Due to that the CFRP cable force is

increasing. In winter it is opposite. Most remarkable is that the average of the cable force is a horizontal straight line (Figure 14). That means there is no stress relaxation. This is surprising and unexpected from a “steel cable point of view”, but “no stress relaxation” is a typical property of the carbon fibers. The Verdasio Bridge is one of the best proofs for the outstanding long term performance of CFRP tendons.

Figure 14: Post-tensioning-cable-force (red) and temperature (blue) versus time (17 years) for anchorage #6. There is no stress relaxation with CFRP cables. Since 2008 the intervals of measurements have been reduced.

Figure 15: Relative displacement (red) between the “Load Transfer Media” (LTM) and the anchorage cone #6 as well as temperature (blue) versus time (17 years). This relative displacement levelled off after very short time. Since 2008 the intervals of measurements have been reduced.

3.5 Case Footbridge Made of CFRP, GFRP and Timber

The footbridge shown in Figure 16 has been realized as a bowstring arch bridge with thermoplastic CFRP tendons as described in section 3.3. The wooden deck is stress-laminated as a flat plate. It is constructed by placing sawn lumber laminations on edge and stressing the laminations laterally together on the wide face with thin high-strength thermoplastic CFRP tapes (Figures 17 and 18). The stiffness of the lateral tendons is 1.5 MN. The compressive stress existing between the laminations increases the shear strength and stiffness. It is causing the deck to act as a large orthotropic wooden plate.

Figure 16: Bowstring arch bridge.

Figure 17: thermoplastic CFRP tendons.

Figure 18: non-laminated thermoplastic CFRP strap elements going through the hole in the glulam slab to the termination of the pin-loaded strap (see Fig. 19).

Figure 19: Concept of bowstring termination with pin-loaded strap.

Figure 20: GFRP struts (Fig. 17) designed as pendulum columns.

The six bowstrings are composed of non-laminated pin loaded thermoplastic CFRP strap elements. This approach allows excellent use of the high strength of CFRP and great flexibility in terms of the geometry of the strap elements as tendons, and they can easily be manufactured on construction site. The stiffness EA of each bowstring is 18 MN.

After prefabrication of the flat glue-laminated timber plate and the CFRP straps the bow has been drawn. The bridge deck which has the arch function was axially loaded with the CFRP straps and elastically bent with a deflection of $1/75$ of the span. The described bowstring arch concept allows an extremely slender and therefore very elegant bridge design. The first footbridge of this kind (Figures 16-20) with a span of 12 m, a width of 4 m and a depth of the deck of 12 cm was built end of 2006 and is in operation since March 2007 at Empa in Dubendorf. It is fully instrumented. Until today the practical experience with this CFRP/GFRP/timber-composite footbridge is very positive. Also in this case CFRPs prove excellent long term reliability. What is interesting is that the volume fraction of the whole construction is for CFRP only 0.3%. That of GFRP (bracing elements, railing) is 5.9% and that of timber (deck) is 93.8%.

4 CONCLUSIONS

For the 21st century, CFRPs especially in combination with concrete will continue experiencing steady and ubiquitous growth in the civil infrastructure arena. The first textbook on the design of FRP for structural engineering applications [34], recent launching of a handbook [35], new design codes and developments of new products for applications in reinforced concrete will create new opportunities for the industry. CFRPs are poised to become an integral part of the civil infrastructure,

especially in relation to the concrete repair and reinforcement, seismic retrofit, bridge deck repair, new installations, composite-hybrid technology, piling products and systems for marine waterfront structures, and sustainable, energy efficient housing. However, as long as CFRPs are by volume ten times more expensive than steel, they will not be capable to replace steel in daily routine applications. To the best knowledge of the authors a greater drop in price for CFRPs, that would change this situation, cannot be foreseen within the next decade. Therefore most successful applications of CFRPs will happen in fields where problems with corrosion, fatigue, and the dead load of the structure are dominant.

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